

New Coumarins from *Murraya paniculata*

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An extract of the stem bark of *Murraya paniculata* has yielded three new coumarins 8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)-7-O- β -D-galactopyranoside, 7-methoxy-8-(2'-isovaleryloxy-3-butenyl-3-methyl)coumarin and marmesin-4'-O- α -L-arabinopyranoside alongwith 3,5,6,7,8,3',4',5'-octamethoxyflavone, 7-methoxy-8-(3-butenyl-3-methyl-2-oxo)coumarin and 7-methoxy-8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)coumarin.

The plant, *Murraya paniculata* L. (Rutaceae) is known to yield coumarins, carbazoles and flavonoids¹. The present communication deals with the isolation and characterisation of three new coumarins designated as 8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)-7-O- β -D-galactopyranoside (**1**), 7-methoxy-8-(2'-isovaleryloxy-3-butenyl-3-methyl)coumarin (**2**) and marmesin-4'-O- α -L-arabinopyranoside (**3**) alongwith known compounds 3,5,6,7,8,3',4',5'-octamethoxyflavone, 7-methoxy-8-(3-butenyl-3-methyl-2-oxo)coumarin and 7-methoxy-8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)coumarin from the stem bark of *M. paniculata*. The structures of the compounds were determined from the studies of spectra and chemical transformations.

Results and Discussion

The compounds **1-3** gave fluorescence under uv-light indicative for coumarins². Compounds **1** and **3** also gave positive Molisch's test for glycoside. The compounds gave negative FeCl₃ reaction showing the absence of phenolic hydroxyl function. Compounds **1** and **2** showed the absorption maxima characteristic of a 7-oxygenated-8-substituted coumarin moiety³.

Compound **1**, C₂₀H₂₄O₈, m.p. 106–08°, on hydrolysis with acid, yielded an aglycone and D-galactose. The aglycone showed ir bands at 1 710 and 1 630 cm⁻¹ and could be regenerated by acidification indicating the presence of a coumarinic system. The ¹H nmr spectrum of the aglycone showed signals for a phenolic proton (δ 6.50), two separate *ortho*-coupled doublets for two aromatic protons, two separate doublets (δ 6.20 and 7.60, *J* 9.50 Hz) for protons at 3- and 4-positions of coumarinic system, and a methylene doublet, a methine triplet and two quaternary methyl singlets characteristic of 3-methylbutenyl residue in the aglycone. These data were suggestive for 7-hydroxy-8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)coumarin. On methylation with methyl iodide, the aglycone yielded 7-methoxy-8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)coumarin which was identified by its m.p., spectral data, m.m.p. and co-tlc⁴ on comparison with an authentic specimen. The HIO₄ oxidation⁵ of **1** consumed 2 moles of periodate with the production of 1 mole of HCO₂H showing the presence of one unit of D-galactose in pyranose form. Since only one hydroxyl group was present in the aglycone at 7-position, D-galactose must be linked at position-7 of the aglycone part. Compound **1** on hydrolysis

with almond enzyme solution afforded 7-hydroxy-8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)coumarin (m.p., m.m.p. and co-tlc) and D-galactose (co-pc) confirming the presence of β -linkage between an aglycone and D-galactose. Thus structure **1** was assigned to this new coumarin galactoside.

Compound **2**, C₂₀H₂₄O₅, m.p. 122–23° exhibited ir absorptions characteristic for coumarin skeleton, methyl, methoxyl, ester carbonyl and unsaturated groups. The ¹H nmr spectrum displayed signals for coumarinic protons in the form of a pair of doublets at C-3 and C-4 positions, and also a pair of doublets for *ortho*-coupled aromatic protons at C-5 and C-6 positions, indicating the absence of any oxygen function at C-5 position⁶ and a carbon side-chain at C-8 position. A methoxyl group at position-7 appeared in the form of a singlet. The presence of C₆H₅CH₂CH- and -COCH₂CH- protons were observed in the form of multiplets. A *gem*-dimethyl group attached to CH was observed in the upfield region while another methyl group was present in downfield region. On comparison of the data with other related coumarins^{2,7}, it was found that the presence of a *gem*-dimethyl and the multiplets for C-2'' and C-3'' protons confirmed the attachment of an isovaleryl moiety through an oxygen at C-2'. Compound **2** on alkaline hydrolysis afforded 7-methoxy-8-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methylbutenyl)coumarin (m.p. and spectral data) and identified by its conversion into 7-methoxy-8-(2'-acetoxy-3'-methylbutenyl)coumarin⁷ supporting the attachment at C-2' position. The mass spectrum of compound **2** was also in confirmation with the assigned structure **2**.

Compound **3**, C₁₈H₂₂O₈ m.p. 128–30° showed uv absorption maxima characteristic of a furanocoumarin^{4,8}, which was also substantiated by ir spectrum^{4,8}. Acid hydrolysis of **3** yielded an aglycone and L-arabinose. Ir spectrum of the aglycone exhibited principal absorptions for hydroxyl, lactonic carbonyl and aromatic nucleus. The

^1H nmr spectrum of the aglycone displayed characteristic signals for two methyls, an alcoholic hydroxyl function (disappeared on D_2O shake), furanic protons at C-2' and C-3' positions, two aromatic *para* protons and coumarinic protons at C-3 and C-4 positions respectively. The mass spectrum of the aglycone exhibited m/z at 246 (M^+ , 100%) corresponding to base peak. This together with the presence of peaks at m/z 187 (90%) and 160 (35%) suggest a furanocoumarin nucleus. These data closely resemble to that of marmesin⁴. Isolation of acetone and umbelliferone-6-carboxylic acid on CrO_3 oxidation and anhydromarmesin (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁴ by P_2O_5 from the aglycone confirms the structure as marmesin. HIO_4 oxidation on compound 3 confirmed arabinopyranose structure.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Electronic spectra (EtOH) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on an Acculab 10 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a CFT instrument with TMS as internal standard at 90 MHz and mass spectra on a JMS D-300 spectrometer. The analytical data of the compounds were found satisfactory.

Extraction and isolation : The stem bark (2 kg) of *M. paniculata* (procured from United Chemical and Allied Products, Calcutta) was successively extracted with hexane, C_6H_6 and CHCl_3 . The hexane extract was subjected on Si-gel column and eluted with hexane- C_6H_6 (5 : 5) and petroleum ether- C_6H_6 (2 : 8) mixture. The hexane- C_6H_6 eluate was concentrated to give a light yellow crystalline compound, m.p. 124–26°, $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_{10}$ (M^+ 462); λ_{max} 330, 270 (infl.), 260 and 210; ν_{max} 2 870, 1 650, 1 610, 1 480 and 1 175 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.60 (2H, s, H-2' and H-6'), 4.10 (s, 8 \times OCH_3), which was found to be identical with exotixin (m.m.p. and co-tlc, isolated from the leaves of *M. paniculata*⁹). The petroleum ether- C_6H_6 eluate was concentrated to afford a crystalline compound, m.p. 128–30°,

$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ 258); λ_{max} 325, 258, 250 and 218 nm; ν_{max} 1 730 (δ -lactone), 1 680 (C=O), 1 615 (unsat.) 1 580 (aromatic) and 950 ($\text{C}-\text{methyl}$) and 950 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$); δ 7.65 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4), 7.40 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-5), 6.90 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-6), 6.30 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 6.20 and 5.90 (m, exomethylene), 4.30 (s, CH_2), 4.00 (s, OCH_3) and 1.90 (s, CH_3); m/z 258, 230, 213, 199, 189, 175 and 69, which was found to be identical with 7-methoxy-8-(3-butenyl-2-oxo)-coumarin (m.m.p. and co-tlc, isolated from the leaves of *M. paniculata*¹⁰). The benzene extract was passed over Si-gel column and eluted with $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6-\text{CHCl}_3$ (8 : 2), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6-\text{CHCl}_3$ (5 : 5) and CHCl_3 respectively. The $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6-\text{CHCl}_3$ eluate was concentrated to give a crystalline compound, m.p. 82–83°, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ (M^+ 244); λ_{max} 320, 260, 250 and 217 nm; ν_{max} 3 000, 2 970, 2 860, 1 720, 1 670, 1 600, 1 560, 1 510, 1 460, 1 275, 1 240, 1 170, 1 130 and 1 080 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.60 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4), 7.30 (d, J 8.00 Hz, H-5), 6.80 (d, J 8.00 Hz, H-6), 6.20 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 5.20 (t, J 7.00 Hz, CHCM_2), 3.90 (s, OCH_3), 3.50 (d, J 7.00 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{C}$), 1.80 and 1.70 (each s, 2 \times CH_3); m/z 244, 213, 176, 148, 133, 105, 77 and 43, which was shown to be osthol (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁴. The $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6-\text{CHCl}_3$ and CHCl_3 eluates were concentrated to afford crystalline compounds 1 and 2 respectively. The CHCl_3 extract was chromatographed over Si-gel column and eluted with $\text{CHCl}_3-\text{EtOAc}$ (9 : 1) to give crystalline compound 3.

Compound 1 : λ_{max} 320, 260, 250 and 210 nm; ν_{max} 3 450 (OH), 2 965 (CH_3), 1 715 and 1 615 (coumarinic lactone), 1 590 (aromatic), 1 550, 1 510, 1 470, 1 270, 1 250, 1 120, 1 090 and 825 cm^{-1} (glycoside); tetra acetate, δ 7.60 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4), 7.25 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-5), 6.60 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-6), 6.40 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 5.80–5.60 (m, sugar-H), 5.20 (t, J 7.00 Hz, H-2'), 4.90 (d, J 7.00 Hz, gal H-1), 3.50 (d, J 7.00 Hz, H-1'), 2.00–2.10, 2.15 and 2.20 (each s, 4 \times OAc), 1.90 and 1.70 (each s, 2 \times CH_3).

Acid hydrolysis of 1 : Compound 1 (500 mg) was hydrolysed with 7% H_2SO_4 (30 ml) by refluxing for 5 h. The resulting solid was washed with H_2O to afford 7-hydroxy-8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)coumarin (aglycone) and D-galactose (co-pc and osazone); aglycone, λ_{max} 321, 260, 248 and 220 nm; ν_{max} 3 430 (OH), 3 000, 2 960, 1 710, 1 630 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.60 (H-4), 7.20 (H-5), 6.70 (H-6), 6.50 (s, OH), 6.30 (H-3) 5.30 (H-2'), 3.60 (H-1'), 1.90 and 1.70 (each s, 2 \times CH_3); m/z 230, 212, 162, 134, 106, 105 and 43.

Methylation of the aglycone : The aglycone (50 mg) in Me_2CO (20 ml) was refluxed with CH_3I in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 for 4 h. The acetone solution was filtered and the residue washed thrice with hot acetone. On working up, needle shaped crystals of 7-methoxy-8-(butenyl-3'-methyl)coumarin was obtained from benzene which was identified from its m.m.p., co-tlc and spectral data⁴.

Compound 2 : λ_{max} 322, 258, 249 and 217 nm; ν_{max} 2 990 (Me), 2 970 and 1 170 (OMe), 1 725–1 710 (ester carbonyl and coumarin lactone), 1 620 (unsat.), 1 660,

1 560 and 1 500 cm^{-1} (aromatic); ^1H nmr δ 7.65 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4), 7.30 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-5), 6.80 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-6), 6.60 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 4.90 and 3.10 (each m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-CH}_2\text{CH}$), 4.70 and 1.20 (each m, COCH_2CH), 3.85 (s, OCH_3), 1.80 (s, CH_3), 0.70 and 0.65 (each d, J 6.00 Hz, a *gem*-dimethyl); m/z 344 (M^+ , 20), 243 (100), 229 (60), 193 (20), 170 (20) and 164 (15%).

Alkaline hydrolysis of compound 2: A mixture of compound 2 (100 mg) in MeOH (5 ml) and MeOH-KOH (10 ml; 3.3%) was refluxed for 1 h. After the usual work-up, 7-methoxy-8-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methylbutenyl)coumarin was crystallised from petroleum ether- Me_2CO (5 : 5) mixture, m.p. 105–06°; ν_{max} 3 460 (OH), 3 000, 2 970, 1 700, 1 625 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.55 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4), 7.30 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-5), 6.80 (d, J 8.50 Hz, H-6), 6.20 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 4.80 (m, *exo*-methylene), 4.30 (m, CHOH), 3.90 (s, OMe), 3.00 (m, CH_2), 2.10 (br s, OH) and 1.80 (s, CH_3); m/z 276 (M^+), 260, 190, 189, 175, 161, 160, 131 and 103; 7-methoxy-8-(2'-acetoxy-3'-methylbutenyl)coumarin (prepared by $\text{Ac}_2\text{O-Py}$ as usual way), m.p. 87–89°, ν_{max} 1 730 and 1 250 (acetate carbonyl), 1 700 and 1 605 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.60, 7.40, 7.30, 6.90, 6.80, 6.20, 5.50, 4.85, 3.80, 3.20, 2.00 (s, OAc) and 1.85; m.m.p. and co-tlc.

Compound 3: λ_{max} 315, 260, 240, 230 and 217 nm; ν_{max} 3 450 (OH), 2 990 (CH_3), 1 705 and 1 630 (coumarin lactone), 1 590 (aromatic), 1 130 (etheral oxygen) and 820 cm^{-1} (glycoside); tetraacetate, ^1H nmr δ 7.55 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4), 7.30 (s, H-8), 6.70 (s, H-5), 6.30 (d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 4.60 (t, J 8.50 Hz, H-2'). 4.90–5.10 (m, sugar-H), 4.80 (d, J 7.00 Hz, arab. H-1), 3.20 (d, J , 9.50 Hz, H-3'), 2.00, 2.10, 2.15 and 2.20 (each s, $4 \times \text{OAc}$), 1.35 and 1.25 (each s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$).

Acid hydrolysis of 3: Compound 3 (500 mg) was hydrolysed with 7% H_2SO_4 (30 ml) and worked up as usual to yield marmesin (aglycone) and L-arabinose (co-pc); aglycone, λ_{max} 320, 258, 238, 230 and 215 nm; ν_{max} 3 455, 2 990, 1 710, 1 625, 1 580 and 1 125 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.60 (H-4), 7.30 (H-8), 6.60 (H-5), 6.20 (H-3), 4.60 (H-2'), 3.20 (H-3'), 1.80 (s, C-4', OH), 1.30 and 1.20 (each s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$);

m/z 246, 228, 213, 188, 187, 160, 159, 132, 131 and 59. The aglycone (50 mg) was kept with CrO_3 (25 mg in 10 ml gl. AcOH) followed by treatment with $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHO}$ to give dibenzalacetone, m.p. 110–12° (m.m.p. and co-tlc). The aglycone (50 mg) was refluxed with H_2SO_4 (3%: 5 ml) and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in H_2O (5 ml) to yield umbelliferone-6-carboxylic acid, m.p. 258–60°d (m.m.p. and co-tlc). The aglycone (50 mg) in CHCl_3 (10 ml) was refluxed with P_2O_5 (50 mg) for 5 h to afford dihydromarmesin, m.p. 138–39° (m.m.p. and co-tlc).

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